

Assessment of validity and reliability of a questionnaire based on the Claim Evaluation Tools Item bank in Uganda, Kenya and Rwanda

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BACKGROUND

Why do people need to be able to assess claims about treatment effects?

Being able to assess claims about treatments (any action intended to improve health) is crucial for informed decision-making (1-7). Belief in false or unsubstantiated claims about treatment effects can cause harm and waste resources. Health systems and individuals face major challenges, including increases in health care expenses and the need to prioritise (7, 8), for example, which new and costly treatments to pay for and which screening programmes do more good than harm. Public engagement – and public knowledge about the effects of treatments – can help facilitate sustainable health care systems, as well as well-informed personal health care choices, through insight into the basis for decision-making. Moreover, inability to assess claims about treatment effects can be a barrier to participation in tests of treatments, when there is important uncertainty about treatment effects, as well as a barrier to appropriate use of the findings of fair tests of treatments when making health care decisions (9).

The Claim Evaluation Tools item bank

Although a growing number of educational resources for improving people's critical thinking about treatment claims is available, few of these have been evaluated (10, 11). A systematic mapping review concluded that such interventions have not been measured consistently and that no complete instrument exists to evaluate such understanding (12). Consequently, we developed the Claim Evaluation Tools - a bank of multiple-choice questions (MCQs) that can be used to evaluate people's ability to assess treatment claims and make informed health choices. The Claim Evaluation Tools was initially developed to be used for outcome measurement in the randomised trials of the Informed Health Choices (IHC) primary school resources and podcast for parents in Uganda (13, 14). However, the MCQs can also be used in school settings for tests or self-assessment, and in surveys to map those abilities in populations (15-17). The MCQs have been developed based on qualitative and quantitative feedback from methodologists and members of the public in several countries (16). The MCQs are written to be used for both children and adults, and have been successfully administered to both children and adults in several contexts (13-15).

Our starting point for developing the educational interventions and the Claim Evaluation Tools item bank was a list of concepts that people need to understand and apply to assess claims about treatment effects

and make informed health choices, named the IHC Key Concepts (18). The list of concepts provides a framework for researchers, teachers and others to develop interventions and measure people's ability (see table 1). The list is subject to annual review and is continuing to evolve. The Claim Evaluation Tools includes 3 to 4 MCQs per Key Concept (15, 16). The MCQs were initially developed in English but some have also been translated and tested using Rasch analysis in Spanish, Luganda, Norwegian, German, and Chinese.

About the CHOICE-project

The Informed Health Choices (IHC) project is an international collaboration of researchers in Uganda, Rwanda, Kenya, the UK, and Norway. The project developed an educational intervention to teach primary school children to assess treatment claims and an educational podcast for their parents (www.informedhealthchoices.org). Both interventions were shown to be effective in randomized trials in Uganda (13, 14).

The CHOICE-project builds on the IHC- project where we will design and evaluate learning resources for secondary school students in East Africa, which also will lend themselves to translation and adaptation for use in other settings. Following the IHC-project, teachers and policymakers in Uganda expressed an immediate need for the learning-resources that we developed for primary schools. However, the cost of those resources is a major barrier to scaling up their use. As part of the CHOICE-project we will develop more cost-effective learning materials to be used and evaluated in Uganda, Rwanda and Kenya. Furthermore, the original IHC-project was aimed at children in primary school. In CHOICE we will focus on young people in secondary school which makes it possible to assess actual health decisions taken by teenagers, something that was difficult to do with 10 to 12-year-old children. It also makes it possible to incorporate examples of actual personal choices that young people make in the learning resources, and relevant policy decisions that are meaningful to them. CHOICE will follow many of the same steps as IHC, starting with explorative field studies, prioritisation of Key Concepts to be addressed in learning resources, development of learning resources and evaluation of effects in randomised controlled trials and process evaluations.

OBJECTIVE

The objective of this study is to evaluate the acceptability, validity and reliability of a questionnaire based on the Claim Evaluation Tools to be used in evaluations of the resources developed as part of the CHOICE-project in Uganda, Kenya and Rwanda.

Table 1. Overview of the IHC Key Concepts

<p>1. Claims</p> <p><i>Claims about effects that are not supported by evidence from fair comparisons are not necessarily wrong, but there is an insufficient basis for believing them.</i></p>	<p>2. Comparisons</p> <p><i>Studies should make fair comparisons, designed to minimize the risk of systematic errors (biases) and random errors (the play of chance).</i></p>	<p>3. Choices</p> <p><i>What to do depends on judgements about a problem, the relevance of the evidence available, and the balance of expected benefits, harms, and costs.</i></p>
<p>1.1 It should not be assumed that treatments are safe or effective - or that they are not.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Treatments can cause harms as well as benefits. b) Large, dramatic effects are rare. c) It is rarely possible to be certain about the effects of treatments. <p>1.2 Seemingly logical assumptions are not a sufficient basis for claims.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Treatment may not be needed. b) Beliefs alone about how treatments work are not reliable predictors of the presence or size of effects. c) Assumptions that fair comparisons are not relevant can be misleading. d) An outcome may be associated with a treatment but not caused by it. e) More data is not necessarily better data. f) Identifying effects of treatments depends on making comparisons. g) The results of one study considered in isolation can be misleading. h) Widely used treatments or those that have been used for decades are not necessarily beneficial or safe. i) Treatments that are new or technologically impressive may not be better than available alternatives. j) Increasing the amount of a treatment does not necessarily increase its benefits and may cause harm. 	<p>2.1 Comparisons of treatments should be fair.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Comparison groups should be as similar as possible. b) Indirect comparisons of treatments across different studies can be misleading. c) The people being compared should be cared for similarly apart from the treatments being studied. d) If possible, people should not know which of the treatments being compared they are receiving. e) Outcomes should be assessed in the same way in all the groups being compared. f) Outcomes should be assessed using methods that have been shown to be reliable. g) It is important to assess outcomes in all (or nearly all) the people or subjects in a study. h) People's outcomes should be counted in the group to which they were allocated. <p>2.2 Syntheses of studies need to be reliable.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Reviews of studies comparing treatments should use systematic methods. b) Failure to consider unpublished results of fair comparisons may result 	<p>3.1 Problems and options should be clear.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Be clear about what the problem or goal is and what the options are. <p>3.2 Evidence should be relevant.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Attention should focus on all important effects of treatments, and not surrogate outcomes. b) There should not be important differences between the people in studies and those to whom the evidence will be applied. c) The treatments compared should be similar to those of interest. d) There should not be important differences between the circumstances in which the treatments were compared and those of interest. <p>3.3 Expected advantages should outweigh expected disadvantages.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Weigh the benefits and savings against the harms and costs of acting or not. b) Consider the baseline risk or the severity of the symptoms when estimating the size of expected effects. c) Consider how important each advantage and disadvantage is when weighing the pros and cons.

<p>k) Earlier detection of 'disease' is not necessarily better.</p> <p>l) It is rarely possible to know in advance who will benefit, who will not, and who will be harmed by using a treatment.</p>	<p>in estimates of effects that are misleading.</p> <p>c) Treatment claims based on models may be sensitive to underlying assumptions.</p>	<p>d) Consider how certain you can be about each advantage and disadvantage.</p> <p>e) Important uncertainties about the effects of treatments should be reduced by further fair comparisons.</p>
<p>1.3 Trust in a source alone is not a sufficient basis for believing a claim.</p> <p>a) Your existing beliefs may be wrong.</p> <p>b) Competing interests may result in misleading claims.</p> <p>c) Personal experiences or anecdotes alone are an unreliable basis for most claims.</p> <p>d) Opinions alone are not a reliable basis for claims.</p> <p>e) Peer review and publication by a journal do not guarantee that comparisons have been fair.</p>	<p>2.3 Descriptions should clearly reflect the size of effects and the risk of being misled by the play of chance.</p> <p>a) Verbal descriptions of the size of effects alone can be misleading.</p> <p>b) Relative effects of treatments alone can be misleading.</p> <p>c) Average differences between treatments can be misleading.</p> <p>d) Small studies may be misleading.</p> <p>e) Results for a selected group of people within a study can be misleading.</p> <p>f) Confidence intervals should be reported for estimates of effects.</p> <p>g) Deeming results to be "statistically significant" or "nonsignificant" can be misleading.</p> <p>h) Lack of evidence of a difference is not the same as evidence of "no difference".</p>	

METHODS

The most relevant IHC Key Concepts will be prioritized for inclusion in the IHC secondary school resources. This process is described in a separate protocol. Based on this prioritisation, a selection of MCQs from the Claim Evaluation Tools item bank will be included in a questionnaire, which will serve to measure the effects of the secondary school resources in the randomised trials in Kenya, Rwanda and Uganda. A similar process evaluating questionnaires based on the Claim Evaluation Tools item bank has taken place in Uganda previously, and the majority of the MCQs for 22 IHC Key Concepts that were evaluated were validated for use in Uganda using Rasch modelling. For this study we will base the evaluation of the new questionnaire on the same methodology we used previously in Uganda (15, 16).

The Claim Evaluation Tools item bank currently includes more than 180 MCQs. An example can be seen in Box 1.

Peter often has a headache. A friend advises him to exercise. He says that people who exercise have fewer headaches than people who do not exercise. Based on this link between exercise and headaches, Peter's friend says that exercise will give him fewer headaches.

Question: Is Peter's friend right?

Options:

- A)** It is not possible to say. There might be other differences between people who exercise and people who do not
- B)** It is not possible to say without knowing how much people exercised
- C)** Yes, because exercise must help if people who exercise have fewer headaches than people who do not

Answer:

Box 1. Example of multiple-choice question

Cognitive interviews and revision of items

In order to achieve applicability and acceptability of items included in the instrument, we will involve children, adults and people with methodological expertise from each country context.

We will undertake cognitive interviews with individuals from our potential target groups to assess their understanding of the multiple-choice questions (19-21).

We will conduct group-interviews in each country setting. Since the initial questionnaire includes more than 32 MCQs (4 MCQs x 9 KCs) the questionnaire will be split into four sections for this purpose. Each MCQ should be evaluated by 5-10 people (=1-2 group-interviews per question set). Thus, in each context we will

need to recruit between 20 and 40 individuals in each country setting. Using a semi-structured interview guide, the interviews will begin with questions relating to respondents understanding of the instructions with the remainder relating to individual items before finishing with some questions addressing acceptability and relevance of terminology and scenarios used.

We will recruit children from school settings who are not previously familiar with the concept list, representing a diversity in terms of literacy, school performance and socio-demographic background.

'Think aloud' and 'verbal probing' are two broad approaches to cognitive interviewing (20). With 'think aloud' the respondent is asked to explain how they arrived at their response to each item. Such interviews are less prone to bias because of the more limited role of the interviewer. However, some respondents may have difficulty in verbalising their thought processes. 'Verbal probing' uses questions that the interviewer asks after the respondent has completed each of the items within the measure. Following each item the interviewer will begin with the 'think aloud' method by asking patients about how they arrived at their response before asking more specific questions, as necessary. We will take notes during the interviews.

The overall findings in each context will be coded and entered into a data collection form, and subsequently discussed in the group.

We will also conduct a pilot test of the questionnaire in a class of children in each context. The purpose of this study is to explore additional problems with the format, time of response and missing response rate.

Based on the findings from the cognitive interviews and the pilot test, the questionnaire will be revised and prepared for evaluation in a large-scale testing of the questionnaire's psychometric properties.

Quantitative testing using Rasch analysis

Rasch analysis is a dynamic way of developing outcome measurement tools to achieve construct validity (22, 23). It is a unified approach to address important measurement issues required for validating an outcome measure, including; internal construct validity (by testing for multidimensionality), invariance of the items (item-person-interaction), and item bias (differential item function)(23). Rasch analysis can be used for both dichotomous and polytomous data (23-25). Since the items in the Claim Evaluation Tools item bank uses a multiple-choice format, they are scored dichotomously. We will analyse the results using Rasch analysis and the RUMM2030 software. We will follow the fundamental aspects of Rasch analysis (23).

Sampling

Instruments can be validated using Rasch analysis of data collected in samples of people that are not randomly selected. This can be justified by the fact that the person parameter and the item

parameter of unidimensional Rasch models are independent (26) and that the Rasch models do not assume anything about the distribution of the sample of people (26).

According to Linacre (27) a sample size of 150-200 is adequate to test for fit to the dichotomous Rasch model and an additional 10 people per response category is needed for polytomous items. Choi et al. (28) concluded that a group of 250 people is adequate for the estimation of the partial credit model. Likewise, studies have shown that a sample of 200-250 people *per group* is suitable for detecting differential item functioning (DIF) (29, 30). In samples that are too small, even items displaying substantial DIF might go undetected (31). Suggested samples in each of the contexts if only one test-set is evaluated would be 150 to 250 for children and adults respectively with an equal distribution of males and females.

Participants needed	Estimated number	Rwanda	Uganda
	Kenya		
Secondary school children	>250	>250	>250
Adults (including health professionals, teachers, journalists and other members of the public)	>250	>250	>250

Table 1. Distribution of sample across groups and contexts

Creating test-sets and data collection method

The test set will include four MCQs per Key Concept prioritised. This will allow for deletion of items that does not fit the Rasch model and consequently may result in a biased test. Apart from selected MCQs, the test-set will include questions about the respondents' age, gender, and additional demographic items for adults (level of education, research training, previous participation in a randomized trial, and health professional background). We will also include a scale including intended behaviour and attitudes related to assessing claims.

Overall and individual Item-Person Fit

We will explore the class interval structure (number and size of ability groups) of the sample and perform an initial analysis of each country specific test-set to explore the Item-Person Interaction.

In Rasch analysis, the ratio between any two items should be constant across different "ability" groups. For this study, this ability refers to the "ability to critically assess claims about treatment effects". The response patterns to an test set is tested against what is expected by the model which is a probabilistic form of

Guttman scaling (23). In other words, the easier the item is, the more likely it will be passed, and the more able the person is the more likely he or she will pass (32). We will this relationship using the summary statistics function in RUMM2030.

In RUMM2030, the item-person interaction is presented on a logit scale, where the mean item location is always "0". If the instrument is a well-targeted measure (not too easy or too difficult), the mean location for persons would also be around the value of zero (23). If the person location is higher than zero, this indicates that the test is easy, if the person location is lower than zero this indicates that the test is difficult.

The item and person Fit Residual Statistics assess the degree of divergence (or residual) between the expected and observed data for each person item when summed for all items and all persons respectively for each test set. In RUMM2030 this is reported as an approximate z-score, representing a standardized normal distribution (33). Ideally, item fit and person fit should have a mean of zero and a SD of one (23).

We will also investigate the individual person fit to identify potential persons with misfit in each test set. If all persons respond as expected, they would fit within the +/- 2.5 fit residual range. We will judge persons with misfit for removal from the analysis because such persons may skew the analysis. Reasons for misfit are respondents guessing, copying or providing "too perfect responses" such as ticking all "A" options in the questionnaire.

We explored individual item fit in each test set to the Rasch model by Chi-Square statistics and by exploring the fit residuals. MCQs with significant Chi-Square probabilities does not fit the model at 0.01 significance level. MCQs with a +/- 2.5 fit residual range were considered potential problematic and subject for further analysis.

When data conform to the Rasch model, ability is measured consistently across the trait level scale with low measurement error. Consequently, fit to the Rasch model implies reliability. In Rasch analysis this is given as the Person-Separation-Index and indicates the power of the construct to discriminate between people with high or low ability. It is also an indication on how much we can rely in the Fit statistics (33). We will consider a value of 0.7 to be an accepted level of Person-Separation-Index.

Identifying MCQs with misfit: Item Characteristic Curve and Differential Item Functioning

The Item Characteristic Curve (ICC) indicates the Rasch model's theoretically expected probability of answering correctly as a function of ability on the latent trait scale. The line represents the expected scores, and the dots represents the observed scores for each class intervals. When the observed scores follow the expected values, this indicates good fit. Items with sub-optimal fit indicates measurement error (23). We will inspect the ICC for all MCQs individually for signs of misfit in each test set.

The item characteristics analysis can also be used for identifying Differential Item Functioning (DIF). Ideally, with the exception of ability to assess treatment claims, the MCQs in the Claim Evaluation Tools item bank are expected to work in the same way for men and women, and across age groups. There are two types of DIF. Uniform DIF is when the difference between groups on an item is uniform- for example that older adults have systematically higher ability compared to younger people. This is less problematic than non-uniform DIF were there the difference between groups on an item is inconsistent across ability groups (23).

Tests of multi-dimensionality and local dependency

The Rasch model assumes that any subset of the items administered to a person should give the same estimate of ability, thus performing tests of multi-dimensionality is essential. This can be done by comparing person locations estimated based on two subsets of items taken from the questionnaire. We will test for this by identifying the two most divergent subsets of MCQs within each test set and comparing these in independent t-test comparisons of person locations.

We will also explore local dependency in the data, i.e. to what extent an item has a bearing upon responses to other items. We will do this using the residual correlations function in RUMM2030. A residual correlation between 0.2 and 0.3 above the average of all item residual correlations is considered potentially problematic.

Revision of items

As mentioned above, Rasch analysis is a very useful tool for diagnosing problems with the MCQs. Revisions can then be made to improve fit, either by revising the MCQs or by deleting them entirely (22). Based on the results from the Rasch analysis, we will consider MCQs for repair or deletion that show signs of sub-optimal fit. The final questionnaire will include two MCQs per Key Concept in addition to demographic and other background questions, literacy questions and the scale including intended behaviour and attitudes related to assessing claims.

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